

Kinetics and Substituent Effect in the Oxidation of Acetophenones by Acid Iodate in Aqueous Methanol Medium*

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The kinetics of oxidation of acetophenone and substituted acetophenones by iodate in 50% (v/v) aq. methanol medium in presence of sulphuric acid has been investigated. The reaction is first order with respect to [acetophenone] and [iodate]. The oxidation process is catalysed by sulphuric acid and increase in the proportion of methanol in the reaction mixture enhances the rate. The order of reactivity observed among different acetophenones studied is $H > p-OCH_3 > p-CH_3 > p-Cl > m-CH_3 > m-OCH_3 > p-NO_2 > m-NO_2$. The plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs σ_p^+ is linear, suggesting through conjugation between substituent and reaction centre. Activation parameters are evaluated and linearity of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger plot and Exners plot suggests the existence of isokinetic relationship. A probable mechanism involving rate limiting electrophilic attack of IO_3^- on methyl carbon atom of the acetophenone is proposed and the substituent effect is discussed.

THE kinetic and mechanistic aspects of oxidation of acetophenones by a number of oxidants¹⁻⁹ have received considerable attention. Banerji and coworker¹ have shown that in the oxidation of acetophenone by Mn(III) sulphate the products are benzoic acid and formaldehyde and the mechanism involves a direct attack of Mn(III) on the carbonyl carbon atom of acetophenone. Radhakrishnamurthy *et al*² reported phenacylaldehyde as the product in CAT oxidation of acetophenone and in their investigation electron withdrawing groups accelerate the oxidation process, while electron releasing groups retard it. In thallium(III) oxidation³, a mechanism is postulated through rate determining enolization, and electron releasing groups accelerate the reaction and electron withdrawing groups retard the rate. The value of Hammett's reaction constant (ρ), obtained as -0.3 , indicate that both the equilibrium protonation of carbonyl group and deprotonation of α -carbon of the conjugate acid control the rate of enolization. Similar studies using iodate as an oxidant are lacking. The present investigation is an attempt in this direction.

Experimental

Acetophenone, methanol and potassium iodate (B.D.H., A.R. grade), *p*-methyl acetophenone, *m*-methyl acetophenone, *m*-methoxy acetophenone and *p*-nitro acetophenone (Fluka, AG), *m*-nitro acetophenone (Riedel) were used. *p*-Methoxy and *p*-chloro acetophenones were prepared¹⁰ by the acetylation of anisole and chlorobenzene. The liquid acetophenones and methanol were purified by distillation before use. The solid acetophenones and potassium iodate were used as such.

Kinetic experiments were carried out in a thermostatic water bath in 40-70% aq. methanol medium in presence of 4 *M* sulphuric acid in the temperature range of 30-50°. The reaction was initiated by adding to an equilibrated mixture of acetophenone and sulphuric acid, requisite quantity of pre-equilibrated solution of iodate. The progress of the reaction was followed by withdrawing aliquots of reaction mixture at known intervals of time and estimating the unreacted iodate as reported earlier¹¹. The concentration of acetophenone was always maintained in large excess over [iodate] and the pseudo-first order rate constants are evaluated from the linear plots of $\log [iodate]_{unreacted}$ vs time.

Results and Discussion

The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) determined at different [iodate] are nearly constant suggesting the first order dependence of rate on iodate concentration. An increase in the acetophenone concentration increases the reaction rate (Table 1). The plots of $\log k_{obs}$ against $\log [acetophenone]$ for different acetophenones studied are linear with approximately unit slopes at substrate concentrations ranging from 0.025 to 0.2 *M*. Thus, the reaction exhibits first order nature with respect to [acetophenone] also. Increase in $[H_2SO_4]$ brings an increase in the reaction rate and the observed rate constants at different $[H_2SO_4]$ are shown in Table 2. This suggests that the oxidation process is acid catalysed. Plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs Hammett's acidity function, H_0 , is linear in each case with nearly unit slope suggesting that H_0 is a more satisfactory measure of acidity of the medium than is the stoichiometric concentration of the acid¹². It also

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TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [ACETOPHENONE] IN THE OXIDATION OF ACETOPHENONES BY ACID IODATE
 $[\text{IO}_3^-]=0.002 \text{ M}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]=4.0 \text{ M}$; $\text{MeOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 50% (v/v);
 Temp. = 45°

Acetophenone	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at [acetophenone] M				
	0.025	0.050	0.075	0.1	0.2
-H	1.95	3.93	6.11	9.40	19.40
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	1.66	3.36	5.28	6.53	13.05
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	0.37	0.74	1.11	1.47	2.93
<i>p</i> -Cl	0.58	1.17	1.74	2.23	4.51
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.40	0.83	1.15	1.63	—
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.37	0.66	1.04	1.22	—

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [H₂SO₄] IN THE OXIDATION OF ACETOPHENONES IN ACID IODATE
 $[\text{Acetophenone}]=0.05 \text{ M}$; $[\text{IO}_3^-]=0.002 \text{ M}$;
 $\text{MeOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 50% (v/v); Temp. = 45°

Acetophenone	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at [H ₂ SO ₄] M				
	2.0	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0
-H	0.33	0.74	1.49	2.06	3.93
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	0.33	0.66	1.40	1.92	3.36
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	—	0.18	0.34	0.58	0.74
<i>p</i> -OH	0.13	0.30	0.58	1.70	1.73
<i>p</i> -Cl	—	—	0.41	0.69	1.17
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	—	0.11	0.24	0.37	0.83
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	—	0.09	0.17	0.33	0.66

indicates the absence of water molecule participation in the rate limiting step. An investigation of reaction rates at different proportions of methanol and water shows that increase in the percentage of methanol enhances the rate (Table 3). Further, a plot of log

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON THE OXIDATION OF ACETOPHENONES BY ACID IODATE
 $[\text{Acetophenone}]=0.05 \text{ M}$; $[\text{IO}_3^-]=0.002 \text{ M}$;
 $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]=3.0 \text{ M}$; Temp. = 45°

Acetophenone	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ at % MeOH			
	40	50	60	70
-H	1.18	1.49	1.92	3.31
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	0.91	1.40	1.84	2.69
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	—	0.34	0.61	0.80
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	0.36	0.58	0.94	1.39
<i>p</i> -Cl	0.27	0.41	0.61	1.04
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.12	0.24	0.36	0.70
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.11	0.18	0.24	0.44

k_{obs} as a function of the reciprocal of the dielectric constant of the medium gives a straight line with a positive slope. This positive slope is indicative of the participation of a cation and a dipole in the rate controlling step in accordance with Amis treatment of rate data^{1,8} at various dielectric constants of the medium.

To study the effect of temperature, the reactions were carried out in the temperature range of 30-50° and the pseudo-first order rate constants evaluated for different acetophenones. The Arrhenius parameters determined are given in Table 4. The high negative entropy values are in consonance with a rigid transition state^{1,4}. A constancy in free energy of activation ΔG^\ddagger (99 ± 3 kJ mol⁻¹) in all the acetophenones studied suggests that probably a similar

TABLE 4—ORDER OF REACTIVITY AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS IN THE OXIDATION OF ACETOPHENONES BY ACID IODATE
 $[\text{Acetophenone}]=0.1 \text{ M}$; $[\text{IO}_3^-]=0.002 \text{ M}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]=4.0 \text{ M}$;
 $\text{MeOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 50% (v/v); Temp. = 45°

Acetophenone	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4$ (sec ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)
-H	9.40	78.8	55.8	96.5
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	6.53	58.0	124.2	97.5
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	1.47	65.0	114.4	101.4
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	4.04	60.6	120.1	98.8
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	2.46	62.5	118.2	100.1
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.23	61.2	122.9	100.3
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	1.27	66.3	111.6	101.8
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	1.13	45.6	177.9	102.1

type of mechanism prevails. The plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger is linear with a correlation coefficient of 0.985 (Fig. 1) and the isokinetic temperature, β , evaluated (265.6 K) is less than the experimental range of temperature (303-323 K) indicating that the reaction is enthalpy controlled. Exner's plot of log k_{obs} (at 50°) against log k_{obs} (at 35°) is also linear ($r=0.96$) (Fig. 1) showing the existence of isokinetic relationship. The isokinetic temperature, β , obtained from the slope of the above plot (258 K) is in close agreement with the value calculated from isokinetic plot.

The reaction system did not induce polymerisation of added acrylonitrile thus establishing the absence of free radicals. The product isolated was characterised to be ω -methoxy- ω' -diiodo acetophenone by analysing the mass spectrum.

Based on these experimental facts a probable mechanism of oxidation is proposed as shown in Scheme 1. In this mechanism, the active species of

Scheme 1

the oxidant is IO_2^+ . There is much evidence^{1,5} to support the existence of IO_2^+ . The facts that under our experimental conditions bromination of acetophenone is faster than the rate of oxidation by iodate and the first order dependence of rate on oxidant concentration rule out the possibility of enolisation step being rate controlling. The following rate expression can be derived from the

Fig. 1. \circ Hammett's plot of $\log k_{obs} + 5$ vs σ_p^+
 \square Exner's plot of $\log k_{50} + 5$ vs $\log k_{35} + 5$ \bullet Isokinetic plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger
 1. -H, 2. *p*-OCH₃, 3. *m*-OCH₃, 4. *p*-CH₃, 5. *m*-CH₃, 6. *p*-Cl, 7. *p*-NO₂, 8. *m*-NO₂

mechanism, which is in tune with our experimental observation.

$$-\frac{d[IO_3^-]}{dt} = K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{Acetophenone}] [IO_3^-] h_0$$

A perusal of rate data given in Table 4 indicates that substituents attached to the phenyl ring retard the rate irrespective of the sign of the Hammett's substituent constant σ . Our attempt to correlate $\log k_{obs}$ with Hammett's substituent constant σ resulted in a scattergram. However, correlation of $\log k_{obs}$ with enhanced σ values (σ_p^+)^{18a} yields a linear plot ($r=0.965$) (Fig. 1) with an exception to unsubstituted compound. This better correlation of observed rate constant with σ_p^+ rather than with σ suggests the existence of through-conjugation between the reaction centre and the substituent. The order of reactivity among the various acetophenones studied is $H > p\text{-OCH}_3 > p\text{-CH}_3 > p\text{-Cl} > m\text{-CH}_3 > m\text{-OCH}_3 > p\text{-NO}_2 > m\text{-NO}_2$. The low reactivity of *meta*-isomers compared to respective *para*-isomers is attributed to the absence of resonance interaction between the substituent and the reaction centre. In the present case the unsubstituted compound deviates from the $\log k_{obs}$ vs σ_p^+ plot. However, when the rate constants are extrapolated to 3° and the corresponding rate constants are correlated with σ_p^+ the deviation

of the rate constant of unsubstituted compound disappears and the order of the reactivity obtained is $p\text{-OCH}_3 > p\text{-CH}_3 > H > p\text{-Cl} > m\text{-CH}_3 > m\text{-OCH}_3 > p\text{-NO}_2$. This type of variation of the order of reactivity with temperature can be explained as being due to the non-proportionality of free energy of activation ΔG^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger leading to a breakdown of the Hammett equation^{18b} at temperatures other than 3° in the present case. The ρ value obtained at this temperature is -0.52 . A negative ρ value suggests electrophilic attack of IO_3^- on methyl carbon atom in the rate determining step.

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